
Characterization of the Scientific Applications Requirements: An Hybrid Approach Using Machine Learning and Roofline

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Abstract

Understanding the requirements of the scientific applications should guide the use of computational resources in High Performance Computing systems in order to improve the balance between performance and energy consumption. In this work we propose a combination of the Machine Learning (ML) algorithms and the Roofline model to characterize the performance of the scientific applications through hardware events and the Arithmetic Intensity, the core parameter behind Roofline. The Roofline has been used as an auxiliary method for both the analysis of the performance results and for feature construction used in the training of the ML algorithms. Nine benchmarks of the NAS suite were executed and the hardware events were collected. These experimental results are used to train a Decision Tree Classifier focusing on the characterization of the scientific applications according to the performance metrics and its numerical methods. The impact of the Roofline parameters in the construction of this model was very positive and the hybrid approach has been shown to be quite effective to characterize the performance of the scientific applications.

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1 Introduction

The use of High-Performance Computing (HPC) has become fundamental in order to discover new knowledge and therefore its use has become crucial to scientific research across many research domains. Despite the impressive advances, several areas of science are still too complex for the available resources and should benefit from the HPC growth, as expected for the next generation of exascale supercomputing¹. On the other hand, with the increase of computational capability, there is an increase in the power consumption, which will be even more representative with the upcoming exascale. Thus, the search for approaches to increase the performance of the scientific applications while keeping it energy efficient has been in great demand.

To reach this, understanding and characterizing the performance of these applications, in different architectures, becomes indispensable for the efficient use of computational resources and energy consumption. In addition, we need to be able to define what are their main computational requirements. However, one of the biggest challenges has been identifying the aspects that limit application performance and their relationship with the hardware and energy consumption.

In this context, Machine Learning (ML) techniques have been used to make predictions and discover knowledge about scientific applications and architectures, aiming to improve the HPC systems. Also, using Roofline (Williams et al. 2009) model is possible to characterize the performance of the scientific applications through the Arithmetic Intensity (operations per traffic byte), the floating-point performance (operations per second) and the bandwidth.

In this work we propose a hybrid approach using ML and the Roofline model with the aim of characterize the performance of the scientific applications through hardware events and how they are relate to different HPC architectures, and the impact of this relationship on performance. A supervised ML algorithm (Decision Tree) is applied mainly to address the characterization of the scientific application problem. The Roofline model has been used as an auxiliary method for both the the performance analysis of the applications and also for feature engineering in the training of the ML algorithm.

This work is organized as follow: the background and the related works are presented in Section 2.1. The methodology for the experiments, details about the applications, collected performance counters and parameters are presented in Section 3. The experiments and results in Section 4. Finally, the final considerations in Section 5.

2 Background and Related Works

Machine Learning can be defined as an Artificial Intelligence subarea that searches for computational methods related to the automatic acquisition of new knowledge, new abilities and new forms of organizing the existent knowledge (Mitchell 1998). ML can be classified according to the amount and type of supervision they get during training. When the training data you feed to the algorithm includes the desired solutions, called labels, we have a typical supervised learning task. In classification, a supervised ML task, the learning process is presented with a set of classified examples from which it is expected to learn a way of classifying

¹10¹⁸ flops

unseen examples. Classification is a supervised task, because, in a sense, the learning process operates under supervision by being provided with the actual outcome for each of the training examples (Gritz et al. 2019).

In this work we use Decision Tree (DT), a supervised ML algorithms that can perform classification task that predict values of a target feature by learning simple decision rules inferred from a training dataset. The decision by its use was based on the success of this model to learn over numerical values. Also, it is not sensible to missing values, noise data and outliers. In addition, DTs are good for feature selection, since the top nodes on which the tree is split are essentially the most important variables within the dataset. Finally, the results are very intuitive and easy to explain, which could help us to understand how the hardware and Roofline parameters are related with the computational requirements of the scientific applications (Klôh et al. 2019). Our purpose is building a model that can predict whether a application is intensive in memory or CPU.

Roofline (Williams et al. 2009) is a methodology that relates the performance of the processor by memory traffic, pointing out the bottlenecks of the application and possible forms of optimizations. Also, to presenting optimization techniques and the maximum attainable performance of an application, it is also a way to categorize the application in CPU intensive or Memory intensive, visually. The parameters used by this model are the Arithmetic Intensity (operations per traffic byte), the floating-point performance (operations per second) and the bandwidth. The arithmetic intensity, which is obtained through a relationship between the prior parameters, suggests the application category. If the floating-point performance divided by the bandwidth is less than the peak floating-point performance divided by the peak bandwidth, the application can be categorized as memory intensive, otherwise, intensive in processing.

2.1 Related Works

Some works use ML based modeling to predict the performance of different HPC systems. In (Malakar et al. 2018) the authors present a benchmark study evaluating eleven ML techniques for modeling the performance of four representative scientific applications. They assess the impact of feature engineering, the size of the training set and the extrapolation on the prediction accuracy on four different architectures. The study in (Amaris Gonzalez et al. 2016) compares three different ML techniques with an analytical model to predict the performance of nine applications executed over nine distinct GPUs. In both studies, they trained the models individually for each architecture, but don't have a generic model for different systems.

Other works use the approach to define an application signature, like ours, as important to predict performance, such as (Bianchini et al. 2020), (Wong et al. 2015) and (Carrington et al. 2013). (Wong create a parallel signature for performance prediction to characterize the behavior of message-passing applications on different systems. The study achieved high prediction accuracy. However, a significant effort was spent on instrumenting the code and trace collection. (Carrington et al. 2013) used application signature, machine profile, mapping the operations required by the applications to the expected behavior on machine with a convolution method ² to predict performance. The work includes a collection of specific architecture and hardware information. (Bianchini et al. 2020) addresses many relevant issues to manage cloud systems using ML techniques. They developed a Central Resource that uses ML to provide information about the workload and the infrastructure to manage resources on Azure's cloud. The system uses two ML techniques (Logistic Regression and Gradient Boosting Trees) and two techniques without ML. According to the authors, the use of the Gradient Boosting Trees is the more

²It is a mathematical operation on two functions that produce a third function.

efficient. Good precision and accuracy were obtained, mainly for application signatures never seen before. They claim that is because new applications present the same primary, behavior most of the time. It is currently unclear how is the best integration with the cloud resource manager and the challenge is to define exactly how and where ML should be embedded in the platforms.

3 Experimental Methodology and Setup

The methodology adopted in this work consists of four phases:

- i) **Design of the experiments:** creating proper experimental setup, including the definition of infrastructure, scientific applications, problem sizes and parallelism configuration;
- ii) **Collecting the performance counters and parameters:** running the applications and collecting performance counters and parameters from Roofline;
- iii) **Monitoring analysis:** providing feedback to applications requirements and hardware interactions;
- iv) **Classifying applications:** creating ML experiments to classify the applications with measured performance counters and parameters.

The phases *i)* and *ii)* are presented below, and *iii)* and *iv)* in Section 4.

Design of Experiments:

The experimental setup consists of applications from the NAS Parallel Benchmark suite and OpenMP implementation model, which offers a set of applications derived from Computational Fluid Dynamics (CFD). They were designed to help evaluate the performance of parallel supercomputers, including a range of problem sizes. The Table 1 presents the applications executed, the problem sizes³ and their computational requirements⁴. Each application was executed 30 times across a predefined thread interval (1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10, 12) in order to observe the difference in the execution time and how it impacts on the performance counters. This detailed information is used to compose the dataset with over 7000 examples in order to be used as training data for ML experiments, as detailed next.

<i>Applications</i>	Problem Sizes	C. Requirements
IS - <i>Integer Sort</i>	A, B, C	MEM
EP - <i>Embarrassingly Parallel</i>	W, A, B, C	CPU
CG - <i>Conjugate Gradient</i>	W, A, B, C	MEM
MG - <i>Multi-Grid</i>	W, A, B, C	MEM
FT - <i>discrete 3D fast Fourier Transform</i>	A, B, C	MEM
BT - <i>Block Tri-diagonal solver</i>	W, A, B, C	CPU
SP - <i>Scalar Penta-diagonal solver</i>	W, A, B, C	CPU
LU - <i>Lower-Upper Gauss-Seidel solver</i>	W, A, B, C	CPU
UA - <i>Unstructured Adaptive mesh</i>	W, A, B, C	MEM

Table 1: Applications, problem sizes and computational requirements.

³The sizes of NAS applications vary from S, W, A to F, as problem sizes increase. A complete description of all sizes is available at <https://www.nas.nasa.gov/publications/npb.html>

⁴Based on its mathematical model and Dwarfs characterization by common requirements in terms of computation and data motion (Asanovic et al. 2009)

The Table 2 presents the configuration of the computational architecture used in the experiments. The detailed information about the processor and memory are essential for using the Roofline model.

Processor (i7-8700)		Memory	
CPU clock	3.20 GHz	MEM clock	2.66 GHz
Cores / threads	6 / 12	RAM size	64 GB
SIMD elements	8	Cache size	12.288 MB
Multiplier-Accumulator Units	2	Channels / Byte per channel	2 / 8
Peak GFlops	307.2	Peak Bandwidth	42.56

Table 2: Computational architecture configuration.

Collecting the Performance Counters and Parameters:

The performance counters and the parameters, which are used by the Roofline model only, are measured by *Perf* tool, which accesses directly the Model-specific Registers (MSR), resulting in low overhead. Table 3 shows the performance counters (*), the parameters of Roofline (\star), collected by *perf*, and its description. The lines with a (\diamond) correspond to events of *processing* and a (\triangle) to *data motion*.

	Feature	Description
f1	* \diamond Instructions	# of instructions sent to the CPU
f2	* \diamond Cycles	# of CPU cycles completed
f3	* \diamond CPU clock	Total time the task spent on the CPU
f4	* \diamond CPU Migrations	# of times that the processes moved to another CPU
f5	* \diamond Branches	# of conditional instructions that alter the flow of a process
f6	* \diamond Branch Misses	# of times the CPU failed to predict the outcome of a branch
f7	* \diamond Context Switches	# of times a process was halted so another could be run
f8	* \triangle Cache References	# of times any of the cache levels was accessed
f9	* \triangle Cache Misses	# of times something was not found in the cache
f10	* \triangle Memory Load	# of times data was stored on the memory
f11	* \triangle L1 dcache Stores	# of times data was stored in the Level 1 dcache
f12	* \triangle L1 dcache Loads	# of times data was loaded from the Level 1 dcache
f13	* \triangle L1 dcache LoadMisses	# of times data was not found in the Level 1 dcache
f14	* \triangle LLC Stores	# of times that data was stored in the Last Level cache
f15	* \triangle LLC Store Misses	# of times data failed to be stored in the Last Level cache
f16	* \triangle LLC Loads	# of times data was loaded from the Last Level cache
f17	Threads	# of threads - Threads Level Parallelism (TLP)
f18	Runtime	The time spent to execution the application
f19	Problem size	Problem size to execution the application
f20	C. Requirement	the computational requirement of application (CPU or MEM)
f21	Application's name	the name of application
f22	* \diamond GFlops	# Floating point operations per second
f23	* \triangle Bandwidth	# DRAM memory transmission capacity
f24	* \diamond \triangle Arithmetic Intensity	# FLOPs performed relative to the amount of memory accesses

Table 3: Performance counters and parameters measured in the experiments. Set of features for ML task.

From this experimental set, it was developed the ML experiments, described in Section 4.2, whose aim is to characterize these applications according to its computational requirements, mainly in terms of processing and data motion events.

4 Results

This section presents the results for phases *iii*) Monitoring analysis and *iv*) Classifying applications, described in Section 3.

4.1 Monitoring Analysis

This section presents the results for the collecting performance counters and parameters phase collected during the execution of the applications. The purpose of these experiments is to characterize the performance of the scientific applications through collected events and its relationship with the computational requirements.

Figure 1 shows the results of the performance counters measured by *perf* for each application and their respective problem sizes. For these multidimensional graphic each axis from the center represents a performance counter and the length of each axis is proportional to the magnitude of the occurrence of the performance counter. The blue, orange, yellow, and green areas correspond to the magnitudes of the performance counters for sizes W, A, B, and C, respectively. For spacing reasons, only the graphics for executions with 10 threads were presented.

Looking at Figure 1(a), Figure 1(c), Figure 1(f) and Figure 1(h) referring to the BT, EP, LU and SP applications (CPU intensive), we can see the greater magnitude of occurrence of performance counters related to CPU events, mainly instructions and cycles (f1 and f2). Also, for BT, LU and SP applications, performance counters related to memory events (from f8 to f16) also occurred at a high magnitude. This shows that, although the main requirement of these applications is CPU, they also have important memory usage characteristics. This analysis is also presented in the study by (Ferro 2015), where it is shown that CPU intensive applications can also make intensive use of memory traffic.

In contrast to performance counters for CPU intensive applications, Figure 1(b), Figure 1(d), Figure 1(e), Figure 1(g) and Figure 1(i), referring to the MG, FT, IS, CG and UA applications (memory intensive), show lesser occurrence of CPU events.

Figure 2 presents the results for parameters of the Roofline for each application, where the Y-axis to the left present the performance counters f22 (blue bar) and f23 (red bar) and the Y-axis to the right, the parameter f24 (yellow line).

Observing the parameters obtained from the Roofline methods, we noticed that CPU intensive applications – Figure 2(a), Figure 2(c), Figure 2(f) and Figure 2(h) – have GFlops (f22) larger than memory intensive applications – Figure 2(b), Figure 2(d), Figure 2(e), Figure 2(g) and Figure 2(i). In contrast, memory intensive applications have a higher Bandwidth (f23) than CPU intensive applications.

A better relationship among these parameters is shown through the Arithmetic Intensity (f24) parameter, which presents higher values for CPU intensive applications. However, the magnitude of this parameter changes according to the problem size executed. This difference can be seen in Figure 2(a), where the value of f24 is approximately $200\times$ higher for size W than for size A.

The Figure 1 and Figure 2 presented the results for executions with 10 threads, however, when comparing the values of the events collected for all executions for problem sizes (W, A, B and C) and number of threads (1, 2, 4, 6, 8, 10 and 12), the events vary in relatively large ranges of values. Figure 3 shows these variations in the occurrences of some events for each application executed. Each box contains 50% of the values for collected events. The

Figure 1: Measured performance counters for each application.

horizontal line represents the median, showing asymmetry of the distribution. The whiskers represent the minimum and maximum of the data and the circles, the outliers. As we can see, the range of values are positively asymmetric (the median is closes to the bottom of boxes). This means that the values of the collected events are predominantly low within the presented value ranges. Then, these variations in the data make it analytically difficult, requiring the use of advanced techniques. Therefore, we use the ML technique to get around this problem (Section 4.2).

Despite the difficulty mentioned above, we can observe an important relationship between the requirements of scientific applications (CPU or memory intensive) and the parameters of the Roofline. Figure 4 describes the acquired relationships between events collected, problem sizes, parallelization and computational requirements. The triangle represents a conventional memory hierarchy, where the memory levels are occupied according to the problem size performed. The arrows show the factors that influence the CPU and memory parameters:

- Bandwidth (f23): is greater when more cache and memory events (memory intensive)

Figure 2: Roofline's parameters measured for each application.

Figure 3: Variation of observed data for selected features.

occur and when larger problem sizes are performed.

- GFlops (f22): is greater when more CPU events occur (CPU intensive) and when

parallelism at the level of threads increases.

- Arithmetic Intensity (f24): influenced by the computational requirement, problem size and number of threads.

Figure 4: Relationship between the measured events and hardware utilization.

All the analyses made so far show the great difficulty to characterize scientific applications regarding the use of computational resources, as different applications may include similar computational requirements. Due to the obstacles presented, we propose a hybrid methodology for characterizing scientific applications, using the performance counter and the Roofline parameters as features for training the ML model. Section 4.2 presents these experiments and results.

4.2 Classifying Applications

In this section we present the results for the experiments with ML to characterize the scientific applications according to their computational requirements. Our purpose is building a classifier that can predict whether an application is intensive in memory or CPU according to the target feature *C. Requirement* (feature f20 in Table 3): CPU (3360 examples) or MEM (3946 examples). In addition, by using a DT algorithm, that is not a black box algorithm (like the Neural Networks), we also want to understand how these hardware parameters could be related with the characteristics of the application (its main computational requirements) and the range of values that these counters assume for each class. The Weka Machine Learning software⁵ was used for training and testing the Decision Tree (DT) classifier (J48 algorithm) on the dataset (described in Section 3, Table 3).

The dataset that comprises 7,305 examples was split in 75% for training (5,479 examples) and 25% for test (1,826 examples). Firstly, a DT was trained and tested with the features from the events collected by *perf* (Features in Table 3, lines with *). This tree is named DTC 1.

In Figure 5(a) is presented the accuracy (99.945%) and the Confusion Matrix (CM) for the test set. The CM shows the wrong and correct predictions for DTC 1, with 816 correct predictions and only 1 wrong for CPU intensive applications and 1009 corrected predictions for Memory intensive applications. For this DTC 1 the *L1-dcache-load-misses* is selected

⁵<https://www.cs.waikato.ac.nz/ml/weka/>

4.3 Synthesis of Results

The performance counters collected and the parameters from Roofline proved to be effective features for study the computational requirements of applications. When combined, they can represent the characteristics of the use of computational resources. However, one of the main challenges to characterize scientific applications regarding the use of computational resources is to deal with similar aspects of the use of these resources for different classes of applications. As presented, applications with different computational requirements may show similar traits like some performance counters and parameters, and the magnitude of these counters may vary when different problem sizes and levels of parallelism are performed. This is a challenge but, at the same time, indispensable for the implementation of any performance prediction or energy consumption in HPC systems.

The use of ML algorithms based on classification proved to be feasible to analyze the characteristics of applications regarding the use of hardware resources. It is important to highlight the relevance of the Arithmetic Intensity parameter when classifying applications because it combines characteristics of the computational requirement, problem sizes, and parallelism. Additionally, the parameter was selected by the algorithm as the main feature for classifying applications during training, which resulted in a good generalization of the tree and balance in the coverage of the tested cases.

5 Final Considerations

In this work, we present a study on the characterization of scientific applications using performance counters and parameters of the Roofline model to identify its computational requirements. The DT algorithm was also used to classify applications using the dataset built using these same performance counters and parameters. The first tree was trained using only the performance counters and the second tree used the combination of all the collected events.

Although these results are still at an early stage, the use of hardware counters as features for a classification model and the use of ML algorithms based on classification proved to be viable to understand the characteristics of applications - an indispensable task for applications to guide the use of computational resources in HPC systems, for the efficient performance and energy consumption.

For future works, another group of experiments is currently being carried out with architectures based on ARM and other x86 architectures to expand the dataset and allow a better understanding of the characteristics of scientific applications among different architectures, however, this new stage imposes another challenge, as performance counters may differ from one architecture to another. Also, the use of other implementation models such as MPI and CUDA for GPU will be studied.

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